

A Conceptual Model for Greek and Latin Manuscripts: Processes

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Abstract

Material philology or philology of materials¹ implies a well-defined organization of what we perceive as handwritten witness (both the physical object and the qualities, born e.g. language), which in turn is a continuant bearing traces of occurments².

While continuants, such as the stroke of a pen, the substrate (parchment, paper, etc.)³, or more abstract concepts like letters, marks, signs⁴ are immediately perceptible to the observer, occurments (such as the process of recognizing the strokes and attributing to them the quality of being letters) are perceived through continuants.

To illustrate the foregoing, we could understand the creation process of a Greek or Latin text (specifically during alphabetic writing) as the linear sequence of snapshots on a filmmaker's reel. Consequently, processes as Textual Criticism are akin to a film technician being able to refer to any frame of this reel. In other words, the manuscript evolves entities placed along an one-dimensional temporal vector, where in all temporal instants one can navigate backwards (as well as forward, to prevent for instance manuscript damages), given that this navigation is based on inferences arising from existing material entities.

¹ Zaccarello (2011: 35).

² This approach follows the modeling provided by BFO, a Top-Level Ontology which provides all basic classes ("is-type") and relationships("has-type"), enabling the creation of additional classes and relationships as required by specific domains. Developed over two decades, the methodology is detailed in the seminal work by Arp, R., Smith, B. & Spear, A. D. (2015). *Building Ontologies with Basic Formal Ontology*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: The MIT Press. Complex entities observed in handwritten sources involve listing, classifying, and elucidating all codicological and paleographical entities present in a handwritten text, along with any additional information retrieved, such as details about the person, tools, and techniques used, see Benetos (2024), forthcoming.

³ Maniaci (1996: 19, 25, 41); Maniaci (2002: 39); Agati (2010: 58, 64,83).

⁴ Parkes (2016: 301-307); Clemens, Graham (2007: 83-85).

Introduction

Occurrences play a crucial role in Palaeography and related fields – for instance, Textual Criticism and Stemmatics –, and depend on continuants involved in any process which reflect the stylistic conventions per time⁵, possessing specific physical properties that imply certain relationships. It is evident that concepts like the “creation of a material object” involve a process that occurs while working with material, which in turn bounds the area occupied by each material object. While a scribe introduces (~adds) new material (e.g. ink) into a parchment folium, follows a creation process; what has just been written might also receive additional material (e.g. a horizontal stroke perceived as *cancellation*), a conceptually meaningful mark to denote “deletion” (the well-known Latin note in an apparatus criticus as *deletio*), but no observer can firmly support that this process comprises a “deletion process”.

Similar to such a typical (ontology-based⁶) concept, a “cancellation” ends up not a synonym of “deletion”, but of “creation”, thus a *del[etio]* note – or its alternants *cancel[latio/vit]*, and *exp[unctio/nxit]* – is difficult to imply all the aforementioned relationships that fall into the generic phrasal terms “is-type” and “has-type” as well. The only critical note that follows the ontology-based aspect of the processes occur in a manuscript is *rasura*, which conceptually is almost identical to the “deletion process”. A first conclusion is obvious: philological notes as *additio* and *deletio*, dating back to the 18th century, are not well-defined terms but gain meaning only when linked to the more precisely defined concepts mentioned above.

Image 1: Palaeographic, codicological and editorial processes occurring while working with a handwritten source.

This process classification is critical for Palaeography and, to the best of my knowledge, provide for the first time a solid ground for relational definition of palaeographic terms like *cancellatio*, *expunctio*, *rasura*, and other corresponding Latin terms we empirically use while dealing with Textual Criticism and Stemmatics.

⁵ Petrucci (1992: 35, 58).

⁶ Guarino (2009: 1-2); Arp, Smith, Spear (2015: 1-4).

Transcription process

A critical process widely applied while producing manuscript during Antiquity and the Middle Ages involves transcription, a general class that could be further divided into subclasses – e.g. “copying” – but suspended by Transformation process as its direct ancestor. Transcription of a handwritten witness into digital medium is considered nowadays most important for Textual Criticism, requiring well-defined description not only of all process participants but also a detailed cataloguing of general and specific components of another process: reasoning, valuable for well-defined Textual Criticism, thus for well-formed critical apparatus. To follow the main objectives of the present paper, transcription process is governed by the following relationships:

- **transformation process** ‘is a’ **process**
- **transcription** ‘is a’ **transformation process**
- **transcription** ‘has occurrent part’ some **generic transcription** AND ‘has occurrent part’ some **object transcription**

This granularity level involves both continuants and occurrents, i.e. other processes, and it would be rather difficult for one to disagree with this description. But what is important is not only the theoretical frame or a more accurate elucidation on some palaeographic entities. It is much of interest that such granularity level provides reasoning, that is firm inferences – not only automated, that is implied by an application – but also logical, both in natural language and a mechanic one. This granularity level can provide exact inferences on difficulties otherwise unsurpassed while process trigger a complexity of “many-to-many” type we face while transcribing and critically editing, providing a deeper understanding of further subprocess, like intra-language and inter-language transformations:

Image 2: Intra-language transcription, providing classes for specific transcription processes that imply specific reasoning, for instance “correction” (e.g. in the case of class “from polytonic greek capital to polytonic greek capital”), which comprises an occurrent part of the transcription process.

It is evident that when increasing the process granularity level, the subclasses generated are actually considered inferred; nevertheless they are asserted in the above image to illustrate the multiplicity that a transformation process can generate.

Mutation process

Processes observed in handwritten sources (often in soft substrates, like papyrus, parchment, and paper) include mutations, a Latin-derived term used in Palaeography and Textual Criticism to describe a complex process during which for various reasons – mainly connected to visual similarity and minimal technical processing that falls to the principle “the fewer movements by the scribe, the better” – strokes, fiat stroke parts, stroke and/or fiat stroke part aggregates acquire additional stroke(s). This or these new stroke(s) trigger changes associated with new graphemic qualities, referencing to new letter, punctuation mark, pause indication and so on, thus mutate the initial relationship between an independent continuant (e.g. stroke) and the specifically dependent (e.g. letter) initially acquired. In Palaeography and Textual Criticism *mutatio* has been used over two last centuries quite empirically, referring to vaguely perceived alterations and modifications of topological areas by the scribe; nevertheless, for a well-defined mutation process, sites (i.e. topological areas⁷) are considered locations of material entities, thus indirectly associated with a process⁸.

There are cases of empirical definitions attempting to describe mutation that in fact describe substitution (*substitutio*) or even transposition (*transpositio*), implying that a mother-class “alteration” (variant of “transformation”, in fact) exists, which of course is true⁹. Nevertheless, this granularity level seems quite primitive for the complexity inhering in processes, as e.g. depicted in the image n.2. For a well-defined mutation description, we have to keep in mind that while writing one creates material, i.e. three-dimensional, objects (a stroke, a stroke fiat part, a stroke aggregate)

⁷ Arp, Smith, Spear (2015: 110-113); Smith, Varzi (2002: 140).

⁸ Cf. Tarrant (2016): [Mutation is] a transformation resulting from the morphological modification of textual information into another form; West (1973): [...] a change related to Textual Criticism, an editor’s intervention in the text; Clemens, Graham (2008: 111-113): [...] when the scribe replaces part of the textual information, they consider incorrect with something they consider correct, or transforms this information into another form.

⁹ Duval (2015: 131, 133).

via another material object (e.g. a pen or a quill¹⁰), which are located in a specific site emerging while these objects come into being. Let's consider an independent, a loose leaf, a three-dimensional object, into which a fluid material (ink) penetrates. When this ink is solidified, it acquires relatively fixed dimensions while occupying a specific topological area in a cavity of a parchment substrate, or lies on the surface, at least a part of this stroke¹¹. For conceptual reasons (geometric, actually) a scribe adds a new stroke. Now, if we look at these two stroke-objects, the initial and the new one, they are projected onto each other, although (for physical reasons) they occupy partially different and partially same cavities and surface areas, while ink depth may vary. For such a perspective, mutation *occurs* in a topological area but *is not* that one, and has occurrent part some reasoning like “minimal pen movement to change shape”. This reasoning in turn requires a specifically dependent continuant that is probably considered by a scribe, a class containing primitive shapes or graphics, like the following:

To conclude:

- **mutation** ‘is a’ **transformation process**
- **mutation** ‘has occurrent part’ **reasoning: minimal pen movement to change shape**
- **mutation** ‘is located in’ **over: material entity**

Image 3: A mutation process occurred in Einsiedlensis Latinus 358(610), p.148, lin. 19.

This is a firm, well-defined and specific description that, when compared to empirical definitions, provides a solid ground for further inferences, especially if one aims at moving into more complex processes as collation and editing, critical editing included. In such a granularity level, processes occur in other processes, among which reasoning prevails. But while reasoning implies a perception process, *certainty degree* also participates as a data property per transcriber.

Image 4: A certainty degree as data property of the info provided for an editorial decision.

¹⁰ Gumbert (2010 draft: 2-5).

¹¹ Benetos, Papadaki, et al. (2024: 232-234).

Conclusions

While working with handwritten text evidence on occurments emerge, and processes lasted in the past for a specific time interval and ceased to last, processes that still occur till nowadays, and processes that start right now, when a specialist decides to transform a handwritten text into e.g. a digital version, are complex entities that demand a high granularity level to explore. These entities governed by logical relationships and restrictions involve material, immaterial entities and occurments into sophisticated combinations demanding specialists' engagement to explore.

Process understanding provide firm solutions for Critical Editing and Collation, which in turn comprise the goal of many related fields, as Palaeography, Codicology, and Textual Criticism, demanding controlled vocabulary and well-defined relationships to avoid misunderstanding with similar, but not identical entities (like the confusion between mutation and substitution). Processes also involve human annotators, who may perceive same material entities (strokes) differently, thus having various certainty degrees while observing this or that entity present in a handwritten source.

From a materialistic point of view, manuscript studies and textual criticism perceive text as a generically dependent continuant, an array consisted of subclasses (a paragraph, a period, a sentence, a phrase, a word) which in turn generically depend on ordered sequence (strings) of independent continuants, namely strokes. Any discussion about text corpora presenting other than the above-described granularity may lead to serious misunderstanding.

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